

Validation Report

Validation of DTI transfer standard for soil water content

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Table of Contents

1 DTI transfer standard for soil water content	3
2 Validation process	3
3 Result.....	3
3.1 Organic soil.....	3
3.2 Inorganic soil.....	4
4 Analysis.....	5
5 Conclusion.....	6
6 Acknowledgement.....	6
References	7

1 DTI transfer standard for soil water content

The DTI transfer standard for soil water content is based on the loss-on-drying (LoD) principle but includes essential improvements to secure better accuracy compared to traditional LoD. In short, the system secures more efficient drying and reduces the risk of over drying. It has previously been described in detail (Klahn et al. 2025). The measurand is the water mass fraction, θ_m .

This report describes the validation of the transfer standard using the DTI reference setup of water content analysis (Østergaard and Nielsen 2018).

2 Validation process

A large number of test samples of organic and inorganic soil were prepared with a good degree of uniformity. The samples were split in different groups and 2 x 7 samples were measured using the transfer standard. A similar number were measured using the reference setup at DTI, and by comparing the results the validation was performed.

The sample preparation was conducted as part of the EURAMET pilot study 1685 (see <https://www.euramet.org/research-innovation/search-research-projects/details/project/pilot-study-intercomparison-of-soil-moisture-measurement>). The report for this study will be published as part of the SoMMet project. This report includes the results of the DTI reference setup and the homogeneity of the prepared samples.¹

3 Result

Measurements performed using the transfer standard were conducted according to DTI procedures (document ID 15564).

3.1 Organic soil

The results for organic soil samples are in the table below. The data are also available in an Excel file². The uncertainty contributions only include the contributions from 1) weighing (0.02 g per weighing) and repeatability (uncertainty of mean value). The combined result for the water mass fraction is

$$\theta_m = 19.04 \%$$

¹ Preliminary versions of report and data are available at DTI in Y:\Projects\VP2009239_SoMMet 21GRD08 - Metrology for multi-scale monitoring\Fagligt\1.2 Reference measurement\A1.2.5. Intercomparison

² Data for Validation of DTI transfer standard 2025-09-04.xlsx

with the above-mentioned uncertainty contributions being

$$u = 0.04 \%,$$

i.e. 0.04 % absolute.

ORGANIC SOIL

<i>Sample ID</i>	<i>Result, %</i>	<i>u, % (k=1)</i>
107	19.10	0.03
121	18.88	0.03
128	19.22	0.03
135	18.94	0.03
149	19.04	0.03
156	18.89	0.03
170	19.23	0.03

3.2 Inorganic soil

The results for inorganic soil samples are in the table below. The data are also available in the above-mentioned Excel file. The uncertainty contributions only include the contributions from 1) weighing (0.02 g per weighing) and repeatability (uncertainty of mean value). The combined result for the water mass fraction is

$$\theta_m = 19.42 \%,$$

with the above-mentioned uncertainty contributions being

$$u = 0.03 \%,$$

i.e. 0.03 % absolute.

INORGANIC SOIL

<i>Sample ID</i>	<i>Result, %</i>	<i>u, % (k=1)</i>
7	19.39	0.03
14	19.45	0.03
21	19.52	0.03
28	19.35	0.03
35	19.44	0.03
56	19.48	0.03
70	19.32	0.03

4 Analysis

To validate the method uncertainty of the transfer standard, it must be demonstrated that the error between the respective result of the transfer standard and reference method is within the claimed uncertainty of the transfer standard.

The uncertainty of the reference method must also be taken into account. In this report the procedure outlines in ILAC G8:2019 ('Guidelines on Decision Rules and Statements of Conformity' 2019) is used. In particular, conformity is claimed using a guard band equal to the expanded uncertainty of the observed error (ILAC G8:2009 rule), corresponding to a specific risk of 2.5%.

In the figure and table below, it is shown that the transfer standard can be validated it a claimed **uncertainty of 4.1% relative**, both for organic and inorganic soil.

No.	Parameter	Value, organic soil	Value, inorganic soil	Remarks
1	Water mass fraction, θ_m	0.1904	0.1942	Transfer std.
2	Uncertainty contribution (on 1, see text)	0.0004	0.0003	Transfer std.
3	Reference value	0.1877	0.1923	Ref. setup
4	Error	0.0027	0.0019	TS - Ref
4a	Error	1.44%	0.98%	Relative value
5	Standard unc., u_{ref} (on 3)	0.0025	0.0024	Ref. setup
6	Comb. (2 & 5) std. unc., u_{comb}	0.0025	0.0024	$k = 1$
7	Comb. exp. unc, U	0.0051	0.0048	$k = 2$
7a	Comb. exp. unc, U	2.66%	2.50%	Relative value
8	Claimed method uncertainty	4.10%	4.10%	Transfer std., relative
9	Max. allowed error	1.44%	1.60%	Relative magnitude
10	Pass/fail	Pass	Pass	

Figure 1. Error observed for organic (sample no 1) and inorganic (sample no 2) soil types (black points and error bars). For comparison, the claimed uncertainty of the transfer standard is indicated (red lines).

5 Conclusion

In this report, the performance of the transfer standard for soil water content developed by DTI in the SoMMet project has been validated. The validation supports with a probability of 97.5% a claimed **method uncertainty of 4.1% (relative, $k = 2$)**.

6 Acknowledgement

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References

'Guidelines on Decision Rules and Statements of Conformity'. 2019. ILAC-G8:09.

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